

A few comments about “Principles of Mathematical Analysis” by Rudin

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I wanted to study the famous book

[R] **Principles of Mathematical Analysis** by Walter Rudin,

and to write a series of reading notes about it; but, after a few days of work, I abandoned this project. I still decided to post what I had written so far. This short text is the result of this decision.

1.1. Recall the definition of A and B :

$$A := \{a \in \mathbb{Q} \mid a > 0, a^2 < 2\}, \quad B := \{b \in \mathbb{Q} \mid b > 0, b^2 > 2\}.$$

We want to show that A contains no largest number, and B no smallest. We give two arguments which differ slightly from Rudin’s.

First argument. Given $c \in A \cup B$, we want to find a positive $\varepsilon \in \mathbb{Q}$ such that $c + \varepsilon \in A$ if $c \in A$, and $c - \varepsilon \in B$ if $c \in B$.

If c is in A we have $c^2 < 2$ and we want $(c + \varepsilon)^2 < 2$, that is, $2c\varepsilon + \varepsilon^2 < 2 - c^2$. If $c \in B$ we have $c^2 > 2$ and we want $(c - \varepsilon)^2 > 2$, that is, $2c\varepsilon - \varepsilon^2 < c^2 - 2$. Hence it suffices to have $\varepsilon(2c + \varepsilon) < |c^2 - 2|$ in both cases. If $\varepsilon < 1$ it is enough to have $\varepsilon(2c + 1) < |c^2 - 2|$. So, we see that we can set $\varepsilon := \min\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{|c^2 - 2|}{4c + 2}\right)$.

Second argument. Rudin needs a rational fraction² $f(x)$ such that the three rational fractions

$$f(x), \quad g(x) := \frac{f(x) - x}{2 - x^2}, \quad h(x) := \frac{f(x)^2 - 2}{x^2 - 2}$$

are defined on the interval $I := \{x \in \mathbb{Q} \mid 1 \leq x \leq \frac{3}{2}\}$, and $g(x)$ and $h(x)$ are positive on I . Rudin’s rational fractions are

$$f(x) := \frac{2x + 2}{x + 2}, \quad g(x) = \frac{1}{x + 2}, \quad h(x) = \frac{2}{(x + 2)^2},$$

and his notation is $q := f(p)$. George Bergman explains on p. 3 of the text

https://math.berkeley.edu/~gbergman/ug.hndts/m104_Rudin_exs.pdf

how one might guess this rational fraction. I don’t fully understand Bergman’s explanation. Here is another way to find such an $f(x)$ (which will be different from Rudin’s rational fraction).

Since $f(x)$ and $h(x)$ can be recovered from $g(x)$, it suffices to give conditions on $g(x)$ which ensure that $h(x)$ is defined and positive on I . So, we start by assuming that $g(x)$ is a rational fraction defined and positive on I . The equality

$$h(x) = 1 - 2xg(x) + (x^2 - 2)g(x)^2$$

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²In this section “rational fraction” means “univariate rational fraction with rational coefficients”

shows that $h(x)$ is automatically defined on I , and that it is positive on I if $g(x)$ is small enough on I . This suggests to assume that $g(x)$ is bounded on I . Let $u \in \mathbb{Q}, u > 0$ be an upper bound for $g(x)$ on I , and let us try to find a condition on u which ensures that $h(x)$ is defined and positive on I . Since

$$h(1) = 1 - 2g(1) - g(1)^2,$$

a necessary condition for having $h(1) > 0$ is $g(1) < \frac{1}{2}$. This implies that u must be less than $\frac{1}{2}$. We have

$$\frac{h(x)}{g(x)^2} = \left(\frac{1}{g(x)} - x \right)^2 - 2 \geq \left(\frac{1}{u} - \frac{3}{2} \right)^2 - 2$$

for x in I . Since $\frac{1}{u} > 2$, a sufficient condition for having $h(x) > 0$ on I is $\frac{1}{u} - \frac{3}{2} \geq \frac{3}{2}$, so

$$u := \frac{1}{3}$$

works, and we can take for instance $g(x) := \frac{1}{3}$ for all x in I , which gives

$$f(x) = \frac{-x^2 + 3x + 2}{3}, \quad g(x) = \frac{1}{3}, \quad h(x) = \frac{x^2 - 6x + 7}{9}.$$

Note that Rudin's $g(x) = \frac{1}{x+2}$ also satisfies $g(x) \leq \frac{1}{3}$ on I .

1.8. I prefer the following wording of the definition of sup and inf to that of Rudin: If S is a poset and E is a subset of S such that the set U of all upper bounds is nonempty and has a minimum m , then we set $m = \sup E$, and similarly for inf. The definitions coincide for ordered sets, but not for posets. Example: take the poset $S = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, a, b\}$ with $e_1 < e_2 < \dots, e_i < a, e_i < b$, and set $E := \{e_1, e_2, \dots\}$. We get $U = \{a, b\}$, and a and b satisfy Rudin's condition, but they are not suprema.

1.11.

Theorem 1 (LUB implies GLB). *If S is a poset having the least upper bound property, then S has the greatest lower bound property.*

Proof. Let B be a nonempty subset of S such that the set L of all lower bounds of B in S is also nonempty.

It suffices to show that L has a maximum.

Let \bar{B} be the set of all upper bounds of L in S .

By definition of L and \bar{B} we have for all s in S :

(a) $s \in L \iff s \leq b$ for all $b \in B$,

(b) $s \in \bar{B} \iff s \geq \ell$ for all $\ell \in L$.

Statements (a) and (b) imply

(c) $B \subset \bar{B}$.

In particular \bar{B} is nonempty, so $a := \sup L := \min \bar{B}$ exists, and we must verify that $a = \max L$.

The definition of a , coupled with (a) and (c), entails that a is in L .

Finally, (b) implies that a is the maximum of L . □

Appendix to Chapter 1. Rudin shows the existence of ordered fields with the least-upper-bound property. It seems natural to ask if two such fields are isomorphic. The answer is yes. In fact a much stronger result holds. To state this stronger result we make a few comments. Given an ordered field K with the least-upper-bound property, we assume (as we can) that K contains \mathbb{Q} , and we freely use Theorem 1.20b in [R] which says that, for any x and y in K with $x < y$, there is a p in \mathbb{Q} such that $x < p < y$. Let K and L be two ordered fields with the least-upper-bound property, and let $f : K \rightarrow L$ be a set theoretical map. We denote by

(M) the condition that f is a morphism of fields, by

(Q) the condition that f induces the identity of \mathbb{Q} , i.e. that $f(p) = p$ for all p in \mathbb{Q} , by

(I) the condition that f is increasing, and by

(S) the condition that $f(x) = \sup_L \mathbb{Q}_{<x}$ for all x in K , where \sup_L means “sup in L ” and $\mathbb{Q}_{<x}$ is the set of all p in \mathbb{Q} which are less than x .

Theorem 2. *Let K and L be ordered fields with the least-upper-bound property and $f : K \rightarrow L$ a set theoretical map. If f is a morphism of fields, then f satisfies the four above conditions. In particular, f is the unique morphism of fields from K to L . In fact we have*

$$(M) \iff [(Q) \text{ and } (I)] \iff (S).$$

It is clear that (M) implies (Q). The implication (M) \implies (I) follows from the fact that, by Theorem 1.21 in [R], the set of positive elements of K coincides with the squares, and similarly for L . It is also plain that (S) implies (Q). It remains to show

$$(S) \implies (I), \tag{1}$$

$$[(Q) \text{ and } (I)] \implies (S), \tag{2}$$

$$[(Q) \text{ and } (I)] \implies (M). \tag{3}$$

Proof of (1). If f satisfies (S), then it satisfies (Q) and is weakly increasing. Let x and y be in K with $x < y$. For some p and q in \mathbb{Q} we have $x < p < q < y$, and thus $f(x) \leq p < q \leq f(y)$. \square

Proof of (2). Assume that f satisfies (Q) and (I), and that $g : K \rightarrow L$ satisfies (S). It suffices to show $f = g$. As just observed, g also satisfies (Q) and (I). Let x be in K . We have, for all p in \mathbb{Q} ,

$$p < f(x) \iff p < x \iff p < g(x).$$

This implies $f(x) = g(x)$. \square

It only remains to prove $f(x + y) = f(x) + f(y)$ and $f(xy) = f(x)f(y)$ for all x and y in K assuming (Q) and (I) (indeed, this will imply (3)). We will only prove $f(xy) = f(x)f(y)$ (the proof of $f(x + y) = f(x) + f(y)$ is similar and easier).

Let $x, y \in K$ and $\varepsilon \in \mathbb{Q}$ with $0 < \varepsilon < 1$. Let $r \in \mathbb{Q}$ with $r - 1 > |x|, |y|$. There are $p, q \in \mathbb{Q}$ with $|x - p|, |y - q| < \varepsilon$ and $|p|, |q| < r$. Setting $a := x - p, b := y - q$, we get

$$|xy - pq| = |pb + qa + ab| \leq |p||b| + |q||a| + |a||b| < 3r\varepsilon.$$

Summarizing:

$$r - 1 > |x|, |y| \text{ and } |x - p|, |y - q| < \varepsilon \text{ and } |p|, |q| < r \quad (4)$$

implies

$$|xy - pq| < 3r\varepsilon. \quad (5)$$

Note that (4) also implies

$$r - 1 > |f(x)|, |f(y)| \text{ and } |f(x) - p|, |f(y) - q| < \varepsilon,$$

and thus $|f(x)f(y) - pq| < 3r\varepsilon$. Note finally that (5) implies $|f(xy) - pq| < 3r\varepsilon$. We conclude that (4) implies $|f(xy) - f(x)f(y)| < 6r\varepsilon$. Since ε can be taken arbitrarily small, this forces $f(xy) = f(x)f(y)$.

2.32. Irrationality of e .

Assume e is rational. Let p be a positive integer such that $\frac{p!}{e}$ is an integer. For some integer q we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{p!}{e} &= \sum_{n \geq 0} (-1)^n \frac{p!}{n!} = q + \sum_{n \geq p} (-1)^n \frac{p!}{n!} = q + (-1)^p + \frac{(-1)^{p+1}}{p+1} + \frac{(-1)^{p+2}}{(p+1)(p+2)} + \dots \\ &= q + (-1)^p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p+1} + \frac{1}{(p+1)(p+2)} - \dots \right). \end{aligned}$$

Let r be the last parenthesis. This is an integer, and, the series defining r being alternating and decreasing in absolute value, we get $0 < r < 1$, contradiction.